

GUT–BRAIN AXIS DYSFUNCTION IN INFANTS WITH PERINATAL CNS INJURY: CLINICAL, LABORATORY, AND NEUROSONOGRAPHIC MARKERS

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ABSTRACT

Functional gastrointestinal disorders (FGIDs) affect approximately 20–30% of infants during the first year of life. Despite their high prevalence, pathogenetic mechanisms—particularly the interaction between the gastrointestinal tract and the nervous system—remain insufficiently studied. The association between FGIDs and perinatal central nervous system injury (PCNSI) requires further clinical and diagnostic clarification.

Background: Functional gastrointestinal disorders (FGIDs) affect approximately 20–30% of infants during the first year of life. Despite their high prevalence, pathogenetic mechanisms—particularly the interaction between the gastrointestinal tract and the nervous system—remain insufficiently studied. The association between FGIDs and perinatal central nervous system injury (PCNSI) requires further clinical and diagnostic clarification.

Objective: To assess the diagnostic significance of laboratory and instrumental indicators in infants with FGIDs and perinatal nervous system damage.

Materials and Methods: A total of 260 infants with clinical manifestations of FGIDs were examined. The main group included 123 children with FGIDs and confirmed PCNSI; the control group consisted of 137 children with FGIDs without neurological pathology. Clinical evaluation was complemented by laboratory (complete blood count, coprogram, stool carbohydrate analysis, intestinal microbiota assessment), instrumental (abdominal ultrasound, neurosonography), and functional (electroencephalography) methods. Statistical analysis was performed using Student's t-test and Pearson correlation analysis ($p < 0.05$ considered significant).

Results: Infants with PCNSI demonstrated a more severe and prolonged course of FGIDs, with predominance of flatulence (73.1%), regurgitation (51.2%), colic (51.2%), constipation (42.2%), and functional diarrhea (23.5%). Coprogram findings revealed higher frequencies of neutral fat (43.1%), mucus (52.8%), undigested muscle fibers (42.2%), and plant fibers (32.5%) compared to controls ($p < 0.05$). Significant intestinal dysbiosis was observed, characterized by reduced bifidobacteria (40.6%), lactobacilli (43.1%), and normal *E. coli* (30%), alongside increased opportunistic pathogens. Neurosonography identified structural and liquorodynamic abnormalities in a substantial proportion of the main group.

Conclusion: Infants with perinatal nervous system injury exhibit more pronounced functional gastrointestinal disturbances accompanied by significant laboratory and instrumental changes. Comprehensive diagnostic assessment, including microbiological and neurosonographic evaluation, is essential for accurate diagnosis and management in this high-risk group.

